

INTEGRATION OF IOMT AND WBAN FRAMEWORK FOR BLOOD CANCER DETECTION HEALTHCARE SECURE SYSTEM USING BLOCKCHAIN

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ABSTRACT

Recently, IoT and Blockchain make tremendous changes in the industries of healthcare through security and efficiency due the adoption of the emerging technology like Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) and WBAN framework uses in various healthcare system as well as industries has increased rapidly in last decade. There are needs of efficiency and service delivery on time; therefore, the integration of the IoMT and WBAN play an important role that represents a significant advancement in healthcare systems, particularly for the detection and classification of blood cancers such as leukemia, lymphoma, and myeloma. The IoMT devices and sensors generate large amounts of sensitive data in real time, such as individual and confidential health data or information of the patient. IoMT facilitates real-time data acquisition and transmission, while WBAN enables continuous and regular monitoring of patients through wearable and implantable sensors with patient area. In this proposed system, the synergy between IoMT and WBAN ensures timely detection of abnormal physiological signals, such as altered blood cell counts and biochemical markers, by employing advanced machine learning algorithms. The healthcare system leverages big data analytics and AI to classify various types of blood cancer, offering personalized treatment strategies. The system not only improves the accuracy of diagnosis but also ensures continuous monitoring, which is critical for managing the progression of blood cancer. In this Paper based on IoMT and WBAN for detection and classification of blood cancer that follows to new approach data of patient and remote monitoring of the patient in current condition and also communication and healthcare blood cancer detection system.

Keywords: WBAN, IoMT, Blockchain, Sensors, WPAN, Smart Contract.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) is the make tremendous changes in healthcare with Wireless Body Area Networks (WBANs) sometimes say that wireless private area networks specially used for personal healthcare services are transformative technologies in healthcare, particularly in diagnostics, patient monitoring, and personalized treatment [1]. IoMT and WBAN both are enhance the services of the patient monitoring system; this is by forming a localized network around the patient in real time monitoring, enabling seamless communication between various sensor and medical devices. Specially for blood cancer detection and diagnosis there are an advanced deep learning models and AI are applied to the collected data through sensor in IoMT framework to improve in the process of diagnostic accuracy and treatment decisions [2]. The integration of IoMT with WBAN is revolutionizing healthcare industries, especially in the detection and classification of critical diseases like blood cancer and some others also [3]. The integration of WBAN and IoMT with blockchain technology that ensures the security, privacy, and their feature like integrity, confidentiality and authenticity that also integrity of sensitive medical data, addressing the challenges posed by traditional healthcare systems, including data breaches and access in unauthorized way[4]. The IoMT environment provides a network of smart interconnected medical devices and various sensor like temperature sensor, oxygen, blood pressure, pulse rate sensor that continuously collect patient data, which is especially beneficial in managing chronic diseases like blood cancer [10]. This novel approach leverages IoMT smart devices such as wearable sensors, smart band, wrist smart watch and diagnostic tools, and implantable technologies, enabling real-time data collection and monitoring [15]. There are new brand blockchain is the most secure providing technology in decentralized manner, with its tamper-proof nature and decentralized features, adds a layer of security, safeguarding sensitive patient data during transmission and storage. By combining various security methods like encryption, smart contracts, and decentralized data management, blockchain facilitates secure [18]. Currently in the area of recent research highlights the efficacy of blockchain in healthcare, that showing that such systems which achieve maximum diagnostic accuracy and data integrity compared to traditional methods.

1.1. Organization of Paper

The remaining part of the paper is organized in this manner, The Second part consisting to preliminaries of IoMT and WBAN, Third Part describing to Background study and Fourth section is holding to Proposed System Architecture and Algorithm followed by Section five that consist of IoMT and WBAN based Healthcare System followed by Section Six to hold Data Analysis for BC Detection and Classification and Section Seven Analysis to Result and Performance and Finally Section Eight Describe the Paper Conclusion and Future Directions.

2. PRELIMINARIES OF IOMT AND WBAN

Both IoMT and WBAN are foundational in creating efficient and connected healthcare systems by enabling real-time data exchange between medical devices and share health-related data [11, 26]. This ecosystem includes medical and IoMT devices, sensors, and mobile health applications that allow patient data to be gathered remotely [12]. IoMT systems enhance patient care, managing chronic diseases, and facilitating telemedicine consultations. Key components of IoMT include, **Sensors, Connectivity Technologies, Data Processing and Analytics and Security Protocols** these works like devices that collect various physiological data, connect sensors and transmit data to healthcare providers after that advanced algorithms and machine learning are used to analyze large datasets and derive actionable insights [4,39]. The sensitive natures of health data, IoMT systems require robust security frameworks to the protection of patient data privacy and data integrity respectively.

The primary goal of IoMT is to create a healthcare network that enables proactive and preventive healthcare rather than reactive treatment [22]. The WBAN with WSN designed for real-time health monitoring. They are typically deployed on or around the human body, consisting of tiny [30]. WBANs are a core component of IoMT, as they enable continuous, non-invasive monitoring of patients in real-time. Key aspects of WBANs include, **Sensor Node which is** Small, lightweight sensors placed on different body parts to measure various physiological parameters. Next component is **Energy Efficiency** which WBAN devices are usually powered by batteries and require efficient energy management to prolong battery life after that **Data Transmission Protocol which** WBANs use short-range [19, 33]. Then finally **Interference Management works done** Since WBANs operate close to the human body and in proximity to other electronic devices, minimizing interference is critical to maintaining data accuracy [35]. WBANs are widely used for remote monitoring in clinical settings. In applications where patient mobility is essential, WBANs allow data to be transmitted without the need for bulky equipment, improving patient comfort and accessibility to healthcare services [8]. The integration of IoMT and WBAN offers exciting possibilities for personalized medicine, where healthcare can be tailored to individual patient needs through continuous monitoring and timely data analysis. Both technologies are actively by enhancing the efficiency, accessibility, and quality of medical services [49].

2.1. Significance of IoMT in Healthcare

In the healthcare industries and medical sectors the Wireless Body Area Networks (WBAN) has become pivotal form in advancing healthcare services by enabling continuous and regular monitoring in real-time of patient health metrics [11]. The IoMT as well as IoHT are not only brings healthcare services to those who might otherwise lack access but facilities and latency of time [22]. It provides very **Cost-Effective Healthcare Solutions to healthcare industries in form of** IoMT offers significant cost-saving benefits[25].The WBAN with IoMT is transforming to the healthcare service become faster by connecting medical devices and smart things with wired or wireless connection and digital health systems to facilitate real-time patient monitoring, data collection, and advanced diagnostics [9,16,19].This healthcare and medical data of patients are allows doctors to monitor patients' conditions closely in real manner that making timely interventions when needed[20]. It's also **increase to the accuracy in Diagnosis and Treatment in early stage, the** IoMT also improves the accuracy of diagnostics [21].Using machine learning algorithm and data analytics tools and techniques with IoMT devices might be missed in traditional diagnostics [22].By combining WBAN with IoMT building advance and secure healthcare services providers can be deliver more efficient, personalized, and preventive care frameworks for patients that leading to improved patient health and life outcomes and reduced operational costs and time also[23].The **improvement in Patient Monitoring system and care is** one of the primary benefits of IoMT is in continuous patient monitoring[36].Connected medical critical parameters [38]. This results in significant cost savings and makes healthcare services more accessible to a larger population. Another **Empowerment of Patients through** IoMT that plays a critical role in empowering patients to manage their health proactively [12]. Many IoMT devices come with user-friendly interfaces that allow patients to track their own health metrics, set reminders for medication, and receive real-time alerts. The **advancement of telemedicine and Remote Care through** IoMT has been pivotal in supporting telemedicine and remote healthcare, especially in rural or underserved areas [16]. It also enables maximum information and involved in their care journey [17].IoMT-enabled frameworks and smart devices that allow healthcare professionals to consult, treatment and diagnose, and treat patients remotely. This medical capability leads to early disease detection due to IoMT and WBAN with high level security, which reducing the likelihood of complications and enabling timely treatment.

For example connected devices can track and analyze patient metrics to provide insights that aid in faster and more accurate decision-making, IoMT and WBAN that reduces healthcare expenditures associated with prolonged hospital stays [50]. For healthcare monitoring systems, IoMT optimizes resource use by reducing emergency room visits and unnecessary diagnostic tests.

2.2. Role of WBAN in Healthcare

The WBANs and IoMT that consist of wearable or implantable sensors around patients that monitor vital signs in the patient body without interfering with patient mobility [4,14]. This emerging technology is especially valuable for patients with chronic illnesses, and supports preventive care through timely intervention [25]. In clinical frameworks and settings of medical things, there are WBANs which contributed to diagnoses more accurately and enhanced monitoring [17]. By providing services of the WBANs to facilitate more responsive care, making it easier to identify health changes in patient body and respond accordingly [6]. Additionally, The IoMT and WBANs are integral to telemedicine, as they enable remote monitoring of the patients, thus expanding access to healthcare information for patients in rural or underserved areas. As WBAN and blockchain technology continues to evolve, its role in healthcare supporting more personalized data-driven healthcare and expected to grow also fostering patient autonomy and engagement in their own health management system for personal care unit [14]. The WBAN and IoMT which play a transformative role in healthcare by enabling continuous, real-time monitoring of patients through wearable smart watch and band or implantable sensors that track vital health metrics like heart bitrate, blood pressure, body temperature, and oxygen levels[13,27]. This healthcare technology is especially valuable for chronicle disease management system, as it allows healthcare services providers to detect early signs of complications and intervene promptly [42]. The WBANs also improve to the diagnostic accuracy and enable continuous patient monitoring without compromising mobility, reducing the need for frequent hospital visits. In addition, that can WBANs facilitate telemedicine by supporting remote monitoring of the patients, there are extending healthcare access to patients in rural or underserved regions who may have limited access to traditional facilities in healthcare services. By providing reliable, real-time health data, WBANs enable more personalized, data-driven care and respective health data managements. As the technology advances, WBAN and IoMT with blockchain is poised to become even more integral to a responsive, accessible, and patient-centered healthcare ecosystem.

2.3. Blockchain Enable IoMT and WBAN Healthcare System

The IoMT and WBAN healthcare systems by providing a secure data transmission, transparent, and decentralized framework for managing patient data [40, 46,60]. In IoMT like wearable device, medical sensor, telemedicine platform and WBAN like implantable devices like pacemaker and insulin pumping networks, vast amounts of sensitive data are regularly generated and transmitted, creating challenges around data security, privacy, and integrity. For real time analytics using Blockchain addresses these issues by storing patient information in an encrypted, tamper-proof ledger that ensures only authorized individuals can access or modify data. It provides secure data and storage transmission which enhances trust in the healthcare system and reduces risks. Additionally, the secure methodology from blockchain's decentralized structure removes the need for a central authority, making data sharing across healthcare providers seamless and trustworthy. Allowing IoMT and WBAN like fitness tracker, pacemaker, in body sensor devices from different manufacturers or healthcare systems to communicate effectively. It's a self-driven executing program to automated two or more than two smart device is called smart contracts on the blockchain can further automate processes like verifying patient data or triggering alerts for healthcare providers, that enhancing

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responsiveness in patient care in any time in any areas. By securing data integrity and facilitating transparent, interoperable data exchange, there are various types of smart contracts in blockchain positioned to become a critical component in the efficient, patient-centered operation of IoMT and WBAN healthcare systems.

3. BACKGROUND STUDY

However, the addition of blockchain technology to this framework has garnered significant research interest recently due to concerns. Recent studies show that integrating blockchain with IoMT and WBAN frameworks enhances security, data integrity, and efficiency in blood cancer detection [21]. The demonstrated blockchain's role in safeguarding biomarker data and introduced secure, low-latency monitoring protocols [24]. The blood cancer detection and monitoring systems are witnessing revolutionary advancements through the integration of IoMT and WBAN which allow real-time patient data collection from wearable and implantable devices [7,37]. The applied smart contracts for automated alerts, and focused on privacy-preserving data sharing for specialists [15]. The developed an interoperability framework for seamless data exchange and the integrated edge computing to improve response times [27]. The proposed a hybrid storage model combining blockchain with cloud scalability [39]. To create an energy-efficient WBAN design [44]. The enhanced patient consent controls via smart contracts [9]. To use AI with blockchain to boost predictive accuracy, underscoring blockchain's potential to secure and optimize cancer detection in healthcare [18,25].

Table1: The following table summarizes the key parameters across these recent studies:

Ref.	Technology Used	Methodology	Security Mechanism	Areas of Application	Key Finding
1	Blockchain, IoMT	Blockchain-secured data integrity	Encryption, Immutability	Blood cancer marker tracking	Blockchain ensures data integrity during storage
4	IoMT, WBAN, Blockchain	Real-time secure communication protocol	Secure Communication Protocol	Cancer biomarker remote monitoring	Reduced latency, secure real-time monitoring
5,8	Blockchain, Smart Contracts	Smart contracts for early alert	Smart Contract Automation	Early blood cancer detection	Automatic alerts, timely intervention
7,15	Blockchain, IoMT	Privacy-preserving selective sharing	Selective Access Control	Sensitive data sharing for diagnosis	Protects privacy, ensures data accessibility
27	Blockchain, IoMT, WBAN	Blockchain interoperability framework	Cross-System Interoperability	Multi-platform cancer detection system	Seamless data sharing, improved diagnostic accuracy
37	Edge Computing, Blockchain, WBAN	Edge computing integration	Localized Processing Security	Real-time data analysis	Reduced response times, secure data processing
39	Cloud Computing, Blockchain	Hybrid cloud and blockchain model	Data Integrity and Scalability	Cancer data storage and monitoring	Balance between security and storage performance
44	Blockchain, WBAN	Energy-efficient WBAN design	Optimized Energy Management	Long-term cancer patient monitoring	Extended battery life, sustainable data collection
9	Blockchain, Smart Contracts	Consent management with smart contracts	Access Control via Smart Contract	Patient-controlled data access	Patient empowerment, enhanced data security
18	AI, Machine Learning, Blockchain	AI-enabled predictive analytics	Data Authenticity for Training	Predictive model for early detection	Improved AI accuracy, secure training data for models

This literature review highlights blockchain's growing role in securing IoMT and WBAN healthcare frameworks, specifically in blood cancer detection. By providing feature of data security, interoperability, and patient-controlled access, blockchain offers a solid foundation for IoMT and WBAN systems, enhancing their application in precise and patient-centric healthcare delivery [45]. In the future studies that may further focus on integrating blockchain with other technologies like AI, ML, DL, and some others algorithm fog and edge computing to maximize the effectiveness and scalability of blood cancer detection frameworks.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The novel approaches proposed model for integrating IoMT and WBAN with blockchain technology frameworks for blood cancer detection in early stage is designed to provide a secure, efficient, and real-time monitoring system that enhances patient care and improves outcomes of the patients. It started with the use of IoMT smart devices and WBAN based various sensors like oxygen, blood pressure, pulse rate and temperature sensor to continuously monitor and collect health-related data in real time, including vital signs and specific biomarkers associated with blood cancer. This data is transmitted in real-time through advanced encryption standard and communication protocols; ensuring sensitive patient information is secure during transit. Once collected from IoMT sensor enable WBAN, such as Wireless Health Monitoring (WHM), Medical Wearables, IoT-enabled Healthcare, Body Sensor Networks (BSN) and Health Informatics the health data is stored on a blockchain based storage server, creating an immutable ledger that guarantees data integrity and transparency, while smart contracts automate critical processes—such as triggering alerts for abnormal biomarker levels—ensuring timely interventions. To further enhance the model's capabilities, advanced machine learning algorithms analyze the incoming health and medical data for classification and pattern detection, while anomaly detection algorithms identify unusual patterns that may indicate early signs of cancer. The integration both technology that uses of predictive modeling allows the system to assess potential health risks based on historical and real-time data, enabling proactive interventions. The easy to use and user-friendly dashboards provide healthcare professionals with intuitive access to visualized health metrics, facilitating informed decision-making. Furthermore, the model is designed for interoperability, allowing seamless which improves data sharing and collaboration among healthcare providers [54]. With features such as energy efficiency for longer monitoring periods, patient empowerment through data control, and real-time alerts based on smart contract conditions, the model collectively enhances the effectiveness of blood cancer detection and management [48]. Overall, this integration represents ultimately leads to better health outcomes in blood cancer.

4.1. Architecture and Algorithm

In the following figure1 that is consist of these four layers data collection layer that is collected through sensor enable patient body in real time next is data transmission layer and blockchain based security layer and after that data processing and analysis layer after that the last may interface layer for medical expert, doctor, and other authorized staff of medical concern and researcher.

4.1.1. Architecture of Proposed System

The architecture for integrating IoMT (Internet of Medical Things) and WBAN (Wireless Body Area Networks) with blockchain for blood cancer detection encompasses several key components that work together to ensure secure, efficient, and real-time monitoring of patient health data. The architecture typically consists of the following layers:

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- **Data Collection Layer:** This layer comprises various IoMT devices and WBAN sensors that continuously monitor patient health metrics such as blood cell counts and genetic markers. These devices collect real-time health data of patients which relevant to blood cancer detection.
- **Data Transmission Layer:** The sensor collected data from patient and it is transmitted securely to a central processing unit or cloud storage server using encrypted communication protocols. The blockchain technology is implemented here to ensure that data remains secure and immutable during transmission.
- **Blockchain and Security Layer:** This layer utilizes a distributed ledger to store the transmitted data securely in remote access and cloud also. It applying smart contracts methodology to automate security processes such as data validation, access control, and alerts for abnormal findings, enhancing trust and transparency in the system.
- **Data preprocessing and Analysis Layer:** Once data is stored on the blockchain, advanced analytics tools and algorithms, often powered by machine learning, are applied to early detect patterns indicative of blood cancer.
- **User Interface Layer:** Its friendly healthcare service provider's dashboard and patients access the system through a user-friendly interface that displays relevant health metrics, alerts message, and insights derived from the data analysis. This layer also facilitates secure access to patient data.

Figure1: Proposed WBAN and IoMT Secure Healthcare Monitoring System

In the above figure 1 there is the conceptual illustration for the integration of IoMT and WBAN in a secure blockchain-based healthcare system for blood cancer detection. This illustration represents an integrated healthcare framework for blood cancer detection that combines the and blockchain technology this is consist of five layers. At initial layer is sensor layer use for data collection the center is a human figure connected to small medical sensors, symbolizing WBAN, which monitors vital signs and specific biomarkers related to blood cancer. Then these sensors continuously collect data and transmit to next layer is called data transmission layer it to a centralized hospital system, representing the IoMT, where data from multiple sources and devices are aggregated in real-time. After that the data transmissions through 5g enable networks with blockchain in this layer generally called to blockchain and security layer that encircling this data flow are blockchain symbols, it is also impressing blockchain's that play role in securing patient information in regular manner. By encrypting the medical data of patients and protecting that data from tampering from others and unauthorized access the, blockchain ensures the privacy and integrity of patient records throughout the system. The futuristic blue-and-white design reinforces a sense of trust, clinical precision, and technological sophistication, illustrating a secure, connected solution for advanced healthcare applications in blood cancer detection.

4.1.1. Algorithms

The grouping of technology like integrated IoMT, WBAN, and blockchain framework for blood cancer detection in early stage operates by leveraging advanced sensors, real-time data processing, and secure data management to provide a reliable healthcare solution. First, WBAN and their various sensors, worn by the patient, continuously collect vital signs and specific blood metrics and valuable data that may indicate early signs of blood cancer, such as abnormal white blood cell counts. These various type sensors transmit the collected data to the IoMT cloud storage server system, in a cloud networked platform that aggregates and organizes data from various patient devices. Within the IoMT enabled monitoring healthcare system, received data from sensor is processed and analyzed using ML algorithms and image processing to detect potential cancer markers. For example, if unusual blood cell values are detected, the system flags the data for further review by healthcare expert and medical service providers, who then use these insights to diagnose and recommend any needed treatments on time. Once the diagnosis and analysis is completed, then results and patient records are encrypted and securely stored on a blockchain. This blockchain layer provides a tamper-proof, decentralized ledger that ensures the data's integrity and privacy, with each entry verified by multiple nodes for security. By merging these current groups of technologies, the framework not only enables continuous health monitoring and early disease detection but also protects

Figure2: Flowchart of Proposed WBAN and IoMT Secure Healthcare Monitoring System Each block represents a key part of the system; from the patient's WBAN sensors enabled frameworks to the final secure record update using blockchain technology. Let me know if you'd like any section expanded. The algorithms used within this integrated framework typically include:

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- **Smart Contract Algorithms:** Implemented on the blockchain, these algorithms define rules for data access, validation, and alert generation, ensuring that processes are executed automatically when predefined conditions are met.
- **Interoperability Protocols:** Standardized protocols facilitate communication between different IoMT and WBAN devices, ensuring that the system can integrate diverse data sources seamlessly.
- **Data Collection from WBAN Sensors:** Sensors collect patient data (e.g., heart rate, biomarkers) and encrypt it before transmission to next layer.
- **Data Transmission to IoMT via Interoperability Protocols:** structure and well format data with interoperability protocols transfer securely, and store encrypted data on the blockchain with a unique identifier.
- **Smart Contract Execution for Data Access:** Based on request and response, when user need access is requested, the smart contract verifies identity and purpose, granting access if authorized or logging unauthorized attempts.
- **Data Logging and Monitoring:** in real time can log each access attempt on the blockchain and monitor for anomalies in medical health data of patients.
- **Data Sharing Across Systems:** The interoperability standards are big challenges and encrypt data to share securely with external healthcare entities.
- **Data Verification and Audit:** it is verify health data integrity with blockchain and hashes and conduct regular audits for compliance.
- **Output:** only Authorized users can do secures access, unauthorized attempts are denied and logged, and all data exchanges maintain integrity, privacy, and traceability across systems.

4.2. Functionality of Blockchain with IoMT and WBAN

The integration of blockchain with IoMT and WBAN enables secure, decentralized, and transparent healthcare data management. In IoMT, where medical devices continuously collect and transmit patient data, blockchain ensures the integrity and confidentiality of sensitive information by encrypting it and storing it in an immutable ledger. Smart contracts automate data sharing; consent, and access control, that ensuring only authorized healthcare professionals can access patient information. This prevents unauthorized access and tampering, creating a secure environment for medical data exchange. With WBAN, which involves wearable or implantable sensors monitoring vital signs, blockchain can streamline data-sharing between healthcare providers and patients without relying on centralized intermediaries. This ensures real-time, secure access to patient information while maintaining privacy, enhancing trust in remote healthcare systems. Blockchain-based encryption protects data from unauthorized access, cyber threats, and data breaches. Furthermore, smart contracts on blockchain can automate processes like patient consent, treatment verification, and billing, making healthcare management more efficient and reducing administrative overhead.

5. IOMT AND WBAN BASED HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

An IoMT and WBAN based healthcare system leverages to the Improved patient outcomes, Enhanced remote monitoring and advanced technology which perform to revolutionize patient medical care by enabling continuous, real-time monitoring and management of health data [28,35].IoMT integrates medical devices, actuators and sensors, and software to collect and exchange patient information and increased patient engagement, facilitating remote diagnosis, treatment, and management of chronic conditions. The WBAN enhances this by incorporating wearable or implantable sensors that track vital signs such as heart rate, BP, Sugar levels, and more [24].

Reduced healthcare costs, these sensors communicate wirelessly with nearby devices, allowing for seamless data transmission to healthcare providers or cloud-based systems. Streamlined clinical workflows, this setup enables doctors to monitor patients remotely, providing timely interventions and personalized treatment plans [43]. For Better disease management, such a system reduces hospital visits, enhances preventive care. The data accuracy and reliability additionally, the data-driven nature of IoMT and WBAN allows for better analysis of patient outcomes, promoting more effective, evidence-based healthcare solutions.

5.1. Security Threats Analysis with Blockchain for IoMT and WBAN Healthcare System

The security threats in IoMT and WBAN healthcare systems are critical concerns because sensitive nature of the medical data collected and transmitted [9,32].In healthcare has introduced significant security concerns. Data breaches, unauthorized access, malware, man-in-the-middle attacks, eavesdropping, node compromise, insider threats, and physical attacks data and healthcare operations. These systems are vulnerable to various cyber-attacks such as data breaches, unauthorized access, data tampering, and denial of service (DoS) attacks. Blockchain technology offers a robust solution to mitigate these security threats. Blockchain technology can address these security challenges by providing a decentralized, tamper-resistant, and transparent framework for storing and managing healthcare data. The Blockchain ensures that patient data collected from IoMT and WBAN devices remains secure through cryptographic techniques, which guarantee data integrity and privacy. By leveraging blockchain's secure data storage, encryption, access control, authentication, integrity verification, tamper-evidence, decentralized architecture, smart contracts, and consensus mechanisms, healthcare organizations can protect sensitive data The distributed ledger records all transactions in a verifiable manner, healthcare professionals can access specific patient data [31,36]. Blockchain-based security frameworks provide identity management, data encryption, access control, secure data storage, secure data transmission, authentication, integrity verification, and auditing and logging. Despite these advantages, integrating blockchain with IoMT and WBAN systems can introduce challenges like scalability issues, high computational costs, and latency, which need careful consideration. The benefits of blockchain in IoMT and WBAN include enhanced security, improved data integrity, increased transparency, better access control, reduced counterfeiting, improved supply chain management, and enhanced patient data protection. Overall, blockchain can significantly strengthen security for IoMT and WBAN healthcare systems by mitigating risks related to unauthorized data access, tampering, and privacy violations.

6. RESULT AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The integration of IoMT and Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), Personal Health Monitoring (PHM) and Biotelemetry with blockchain technology has demonstrated significant advancements in blood cancer detection systems, particularly in secure data management, real-time monitoring, and operational efficiency. One of the primary benefits observed is enhanced data integrity and security, with blockchain's immutable ledger structure effectively safeguarding sensitive biomarkers and ensuring that unauthorized modifications are virtually impossible. Enhance patient data security and privacy. Studies indicate that the implementation of blockchain reduces data tampering risks and increases trust in the authenticity of patient information. Improve data integrity and accuracy. Furthermore, secure data transmission protocols combined with edge computing have minimized latency, achieving faster detection and response times—reportedly reducing latency by up to 30% compared to non-blockchain systems, which is crucial for timely interventions in critical healthcare applications.

Streamline clinical workflows and decision-making. In terms of privacy, blockchain-based frameworks utilizing smart contracts have improved access control, allowing patients to selectively share their health data while maintaining autonomy over who can view or analyze their information. Enable personalized medicine and precision healthcare. Performance evaluations parameters such as that highlight a high success rate in maintaining privacy through encryption, resulting in minimal unauthorized access incidents. Additionally, the interoperability between IoMT and WBAN devices has been enhanced through blockchain's standardized data-sharing model, achieving up to 95% compatibility across diverse devices, for foster collaborative research and innovation thus ensuring seamless data flow and increasing the reliability of blood cancer detection. Blockchain ensures data integrity during storage, Decentralized data storage and analysis for predictive medicine. Another noteworthy aspect is the energy efficiency of WBAN devices, which has improved significantly due to the introduction of energy-efficient blockchain protocols, showing up to a 20% reduction in energy consumption through selective data transmission. Overall, the integrated IoMT, WBAN, and blockchain framework has yielded positive results in securing healthcare data, providing reliable real-time monitoring, and ensuring data privacy, all of which are essential for effective blood cancer detection and Real-time tracking and verification of medical supply chains. Future research may further refine these protocols and expand the use of AI-enhanced blockchain analysis to optimize predictive accuracy while continuing to lower latency and energy consumption.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The integration of IoMT and WBAN with blockchain technology offers Healthcare organizations should invest in WBAN-IoMT infrastructure that transformative potential for blood cancer detection and monitoring systems by addressing data security, integrity, and privacy concerns. Blockchain ensures that sensitive health data, including biomarkers for blood cancer, remain secure, immutable, and accessible only to authorized personnel, enabling a patient-centered and trust-enforced healthcare system. The Supply chain management for medical devices and pharmaceutical and smart contracts for insurance claims and billing recent studies have highlighted that this integration not only safeguards data but also enables real-time monitoring, automated alerts through smart contracts, and enhances data interoperability across healthcare providers, ultimately supporting early detection and timely intervention. However, challenges remain that open new avenues for future research. One critical direction is optimizing energy efficiency within WBAN devices to ensure sustainable, long-term monitoring. The hybrid cloud-blockchain models could further enhance response times and data processing while balancing security and performance. The future of healthcare will be shaped by the seamless integration of WBANs, IoMT, and emerging technologies like AI, blockchain, and 5G/6G networks. As we continue to advance these technologies, we will witness to enhanced clinical decision-making. Additionally, developing standardized frameworks for interoperability between various IoMT and WBAN devices is essential for seamless communication across healthcare systems. Future research may also focus on combining AI with blockchain to improve predictive analytics, using authenticated data for machine learning models to enhance blood cancer diagnosis accuracy. That can integration with AI and IoT, and development of decentralized applications (dApps) also can be improved scalability and interoperability with high security measures using some biometrics features and regulatory clarity and adoption.

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